

ISic3610

I.Sicily inscription 3610

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2015.01.13

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Scicli

Provenance

fondo Picciona della contrada Scalonazzo, frazione di Sampierie

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Ragusa, Museo Archeologico
Ibleo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645683

Bibliography

1888-. *L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2008.0598

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Ferrua, A 1941. Epigrafica sicula pagana e cristiana. *Rivista di archeologia cristiana*. 18: 151-243. At 214-215 no.93 fig.48

Rizzone, V.G. 2008. Iscrizioni tardoantiche del territorio di Scicli. In Militello, P. (eds.), *Scicli: archeologia e territorio*. Palermo. pp. 283-290. At 283-284 no.1 fig.25.1

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